

FORKaiA

Title: Machine Learning, Machine Vision and Robot Vision will be at the top of Robotics developers' priorities in 2018

Name: Ali Sina

Affiliation: UCI Applied Innovation Lab (UC Irvine)

INTRODUCTION:

Machines can learn in a variety of different ways and it seems like every day there's a new stealth learning methodology in the works but Machine Vision involves more than just computer algorithms; engineers and roboticists also have to account for camera hardware that allow robots to process physical data. Robot vision is very closely linked to machine vision, which can be given credit for the emergence of robot guidance and automatic inspection systems. Robots can physically affect their environment.

AIM:

An influx of big data i.e. visual information available on the web (including annotated/labeled photos and videos) has propelled advances in computer vision, which in turn has helped further machine-learning based structured prediction learning techniques leading to robot vision applications like identification and sorting of objects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Anomaly detection with unsupervised learning, such as building systems capable of finding and assessing faults in silicon wafers using convolutional neural networks. Extrasensory technologies like radar, LIDAR, and ultrasound are also driving the development of 360-degree vision-based systems for autonomous vehicles and drones.

RESULTS:

Machine learning and robotics is at the top of developers' priorities for 2018, with 69.4 percent stating that they're building robotics apps and 48.7 percent of all developers indicating the use of machine learning in their projects. And it will continue to be a top priority.

CONCLUSIONS:

Machine Learning will remain a long-term priority in robotics due to military contract, massive investments by a barrage of auto-manufacturers, "Drone mania", a whole new wave of Ai start-ups and innovations quantum scaled by major robotics manufacturers.

KEYWORDS:

Machine Learning, Robotics, Machine Vision, Robot Vision, Supervises Learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Ali Sina graduated from USC then completed his Masters from Pepperdine University. He is currently working on next generation AI solutions at UCI Applied Innovation lab. Ali is the Founder and CEO of Forkaia, a cognitive platform that matches data scientists and programmers with AI projects they find interesting. Ali is building the AI ecosystem of the future with a culture built around collaboration, experimentation and disruption and uses the ecosystem for constant experimentation and virtually incubates, accelerates and holds a portfolio of his own companies.